

USING WEB-QUEST TECHNOLOGY IN ORGANIZING INDEPENDENT WORK FOR STUDENTS

Ermirzayev Abbos Vaxobjonovich

Namangan state Institute of foreign languages

ermirzayev89@mail.ru

ANNOTATION

The article raises the problems of using information and communication technologies in the educational process. The use of web quest technology allows you to change students' attitudes towards independent work, improve general competencies (search, analyze and evaluate information, work in a team), successfully perform relevant types of professional activities, mastering professional competencies.

Key words: web quest, independent work of students.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье поднимаются проблемы использования информационно-коммуникационных технологий в образовательном процессе. Использование технологии веб-квеста позволяет изменить отношение студентов к самостоятельной работе, совершенствовать общие компетенции (поиск, анализ и оценка информации, работа в команде), успешно выполнять соответствующие виды профессиональной деятельности, овладевая профессиональными компетенциями.

Ключевые слова: веб-квест, самостоятельная работа студентов.

ANNOTATSIYA

Maqolada o'quv jarayonida axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalaridan foydalanish muammolari keltirilgan. Web-kvest texnologiyasidan foydalanish talabalarning mustaqil ishlashga bo'lgan munosabatini o'zgartirish, umumiy kompetensiyalarni yaxshilash (axborotni qidirish, tahlil qilish va baholash, jamoada ishlash), tegishli kasbiy faoliyat turlarini muvaffaqiyatli bajarish, kasbiy kompetensiyalarni o'zlashtirish imkonini beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Web-kvest, talabalarning mustaqil ishi.

INTRODUCTION

The term “Web-Quest” was first proposed in the summer of 1995 by Bernie Dodge, a professor of educational technology at the University of San Diego (USA). The author developed innovative Internet applications for integration into the educational process when teaching various academic subjects at different levels of education [1].

Kenton Letkeman, the creator of a number of excellent webquests, believes that this is a super learning tool, because... A constructivist approach to learning is used.

When completing webquests, students do not receive ready-made answers or solutions; they independently solve the task assigned to them [2].

Working on a webquest helps

- organize active independent or group search activities
- promotes the development of creative thinking and problem solving skills
- makes it possible to implement an individual approach
- trains thinking abilities (explanation, comparison, classification, highlighting general and specific)

Thus, we can say that the webquest technology is based on an activity-based approach.

Classification of webquests.

Web quests can cover either a separate problem, academic subject, topic, or be interdisciplinary; Bernie Dodge identifies three principles for classifying web quests:

1. By duration of implementation: short-term and long-term.
2. By subject content: mono-projects and interdisciplinary web quests.
3. By the type of tasks performed by students: retelling tasks, compilation tasks, mystery tasks, journalistic tasks, design tasks, creative product tasks, solving controversial problems (consensus building tasks), persuasion tasks, self-knowledge tasks, analytical tasks, judgment tasks, scientific tasks.

In our age of information society, the ability to independently obtain knowledge and improve one’s qualifications is an indicator of professionalism. The ability to make informed, reasoned decisions, that is, to take responsibility, is one of the main values of education. It’s no secret that the modern educational process is no longer conceivable without the use of information and communication technologies. Free access to information and the rapid development of modern information technologies create new conditions for the field of education, in particular for organizing independent work for students.

Consequently, the question arises: the use of what modern technologies in organizing independent work of students will help increase motivation for the learning process, take into account the interests of students, the ability to work at a pace convenient for them, and contribute to the mastery of general and professional competencies?

Based on the fact that a modern student spends most of his time on the Internet, we believe that the use of Internet resources and electronic resources will provide the ability to access assignments for extracurricular independent work and complete them, regardless of where one is located. student: in the library, in the classroom, at home or on the street [7].

In our opinion, in the context of implementing a competency-based approach, modern technologies such as web quests and distance learning can be used to organize students' independent work. These technologies improve students' ability to work with information located on different media, plan their activities, and increase interest in studying disciplines and interdisciplinary courses.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

It is the web quest that combines elements of problem-based learning, the project method, games and involves the active use of information and communication technologies. Even D. Dewey and his followers turned to problem-based methods, believing "that posing a problem and finding ways to solve it and reflecting on the results obtained are the best ways to achieve the main goal - the intellectual development of the individual, the formation of skills to work with information "[3, p. 198]. As E. S. Polat notes, the project method allows you to search for a solution to a problem in practical activity, makes it possible to comprehend theoretical knowledge and forms the ability to find ways to solve problem situations [3].

An analysis of Internet resources, scientific articles and methodological literature showed that a web quest is considered as a technology, a problem task, a method, a form and a medium quality Webquest as a technology is a set of methods and tools to achieve the desired result. Ya. S. Bykhovsky notes that an educational web quest is an Internet site with which students work, performing one or another educational task [2].

According to M. V. Andreeva, a web quest is a problem task with elements of a role-playing game, for the implementation of which information resources of the Internet are used [1].

Ya. S. Bykhovsky considers the webquest both as a method and as a form. A webquest as a method is a method of interconnected activity between a teacher and students, aimed at solving educational problems and ways of organizing a student's

educational and cognitive activity. Webquest as a form – organizing, establishing, bringing into the system the interaction between teacher and students when working on certain content [2].

By distance learning, specialists from the American Association (USDLA) understand the learning process in which the teacher and student are geographically separated and therefore rely on electronic tools and printed aids to organize the educational process [9].

By distance educational technologies, E. S. Polat understands educational technologies implemented mainly with the use of information technology and telecommunications, with indirect interaction between students and teachers [5, p. 12].

Thus, distance learning is considered as a form of independent learning using electronic learning tools, and distance technologies involve the use of information technology and telecommunications to organize the learning process.

Based on this, a web quest can be used in working with students as a form of organization character, attractiveness for students with different sensory channels of information perception (visual, auditory, kinesthetic), efficient use of time during a lesson, as well as the development of competencies, computer literacy and critical thinking. The disadvantages noted were the obsolescence of Internet resources, which become inaccessible, as well as the students' possession of certain skills to complete webquest tasks [8].

Thus, this study showed that the use of web quests in the educational process contributes to the development of students' interest, ensures interactivity of the learning process, the ability to work at a convenient pace, and also allows them to develop their ability to carry out search for information and think critically about it.

There are quite a large number of web quests on the Internet, but they are mainly addressed to school students. In our work, we assume that the use of web quests will change the process of organizing independent work of students of a pedagogical college, and will also help increase motivation for educational activities and mastery of ICT competencies outlined in the Professional Standard of a Teacher [4].

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

At the beginning of our research, we conducted a survey, during which we found out that all 3rd year students at home have a computer and access in Internet. Students were also asked to express their attitude towards independent work.

During the study of the interdisciplinary course (IDC) 03.06 Theory and methods of mathematical development, 3rd year students were offered the web quest “Opening the chest of mathematics methods.” The purpose of the web quest was for students to study the means of forming elementary mathematical concepts in preschool children

and to develop material for a mathematics methodology chest. Work on the webquest continued for three weeks.

Students were attracted to the work on the webquest by the form of travel. First, they greeted each other while working with the linoit service; they posted their photo and wishes to the webquest participants on the online board, which contributed to the creation of a creative, friendly atmosphere in the group. Having become acquainted with the webquest task, the students chose the most suitable role for themselves, according to which they should act when completing the task. Registration on the webquest participants' page allowed the teacher to monitor students' assignments and provide the necessary assistance in a timely manner, and for students to exercise self-monitoring and mutual control to achieve the best work results. The variability and differentiated nature of webquest tasks contributed to increasing students' motivation to study the material and enhancing both individual and group independent work of students.

To search for information, students were offered links to sites pre-selected by the teacher. The use of suggested links and search engines helped students complete assignments.

The first task, depending on the role, was aimed at studying the means of forming elementary mathematical concepts in preschool children. Using online electronic libraries, students worked with textbooks, reference books, dictionaries, studied information, then designed and presented it in the form of a presentation, table or diagram. Completing the first task allowed students to move on to developing material for the mathematics methodology chest.

In the second task, students playing the role of a methodologist had to create a memo for educators on a proposed topic, educators had to create a didactic game with mathematical content, writers had to develop a book for preschoolers, including material with mathematical content in different forms. - literary genres; animators – to select and design a collection of animated films for preschoolers with mathematical content.

Having started to complete the second task, students who took on the same role needed to distribute responsibilities among themselves in order to work as a team and, as a result, obtain a common product of activity. In the process of completing assignments, students became acquainted with the work of fellow students performing other roles, and upon completion of the work, by filling out a questionnaire, they were able to evaluate them according to the proposed criteria. Students also had to self-assess the work performed based on the assessment criteria. Analysis of reflection questionnaires based on the results of the work showed that participation in the

webquest for students was interesting, exciting, educational, and exciting. During the trip, according to the students, they learned to carefully select material for completing an assignment, work on a website with a web quest, and work in a team. As they completed the webquest tasks, each student could ask a question using email or add a comment to a specific task on the webquest website. The teacher, acting as a consultant, directed the process of finding answers to the questions posed in the webquest.

At the preparatory stage, a survey of parents was conducted, a newspaper layout and a plan for working with parents were developed. At the main stage of the project, the teacher introduced parents to the electronic newspaper, roles were distributed among parents and tasks corresponding to each role for the newspaper “Rainbow Childhood”. Parents were offered the following roles: lawyer, animator, nutritionist, tour operator, medical worker, photo reporter-designer. For each role, tasks were defined: for a lawyer - to draw up a memo for parents about the rights of the child; tour operator - to present several tour routes in Russia and abroad; nutritionists - to develop a reminder of the correct diet for preschool children; a group of animators - to think over entertainment for children at sea, in the forest and in the mountains; photo reporters-designers – offer sketches for the design of reminders for parents and entertainment for children; for a medical worker to make recommendations for protecting the health of children on vacation. Based on the proposed links to Internet resources, parents searched for the necessary information. This form of work aroused parents’ interest and desire to find material, since the topic of the project is relevant to parents.

And at the final stage of the project - a parent meeting - a presentation of the newspaper took place, parents shared their impressions of the work done and expressed a desire to continue working on creating electronic newspapers covering information on topics that are relevant to them. The use of modern technologies made it possible to interest and attract the attention of the majority of parents (88% according to the survey results) to the problem of organizing summer holidays for preschool children. Repeated questioning showed that the chosen form of work for parents is interesting, unusual and very educational.

As a result of the work, we found that the majority of students (91% according to the survey results) had a positive attitude towards the use of a webquest when organizing classroom and extracurricular independent work. Confirmation that the proposed form of work

What turned out to be interesting and modern for students was the student’s development of a web quest addressed to parents of preschool children.

The positive result obtained during the study allowed us to plan further work on developing a series of web quests for organizing students' independent work in different disciplines and interdisciplinary courses. We are convinced that the convenience of placing assignments and the ability to choose them activates students, changes their attitude towards independent work, motivates them to study an interdisciplinary course, and free access to assignments allows for self-control and control over them.

Thus, the study showed that the use of web quest technology effectively influences the process of organizing independent work of students of a pedagogical college. The use of web quests allows the teacher and students to remotely manage independent work, allows students to work at a pace convenient for them, and also provides them with the opportunity to independently build an individual learning path.

CONCLUSION

Consequently, the use of web quest technology in organizing students' independent work contributes to the development of the ability to search for information and think critically about it, allows students to learn from each other, control the process of completing assignments, work in a team, coordinate their actions, and also increase motivation for the learning process. A webquest, using Internet information resources and integrating them into the educational process, helps to effectively solve a number of practical problems.

REFERENCES

1. Андреева М. В. Технологии веб-квест в формировании коммуникативной и социокультурной компетенции // Информационно-коммуникационные технологии в обучении иностранным языкам: тезисы докладов I Международной научно-практической конференции. – М.: МПГУ, 2004. – С. 20–25.
2. Быховский Я. С. Образовательные веб-квесты [Электронный ресурс] // Материалы международной конференции «Информационные технологии в образовании. ИТО-99». – URL: <http://ito.edu.ru/1999/III/1/30015.html> (дата обращения: 06.03.2016).
3. Полат Е. С. Современные педагогические и информационные технологии в системе образования. – М.: Академия, 2010. – 368 с.
4. Полат Е. С., Бухаркина М. Ю., Мойсеева М. В. Теория и практика дистанционного обучения. – М.: Академия, 2004. – 416 с.

5. Профессиональный стандарт. Педагог (педагогическая деятельность в дошкольном, начальном общем, основном общем, среднем общем образовании) (воспитатель, учитель) [Электронный ресурс]: Приказ Министерства
6. труда и социальной защиты РФ от 18 октября 2013 г. № 544н. – URL: http://iro23.ru/sites/default/files/prikaz_mintruda_rf_ot_18.10.2013_no544n_ob_utverzhdenii_profstandarta_pedagoga.pdf (дата обращения: 06.03.2016).
7. Федеральный государственный образова- тельный стандарт среднего профессионально- го образования по специальности 44.02.01 До- школьное образование [Электронный ресурс]: Приказ Министерства образования и науки РФ от 27.10.2014 г. № 1351. – URL: http://oaouspobpk.ru/activity/fgos/FGOS_440201.pdf (дата обращения: 06.03.2016).
8. Хлупина Н. О. Формирование общих и профессиональных компетенций при самосто- ятельной работе студентов // Профессиональное образование в России и за рубежом. – 2015. –
9. № 2 (18) – С. 49–55.
10. Cynthia B. L., Zafer U. Advantages and Disadvantages of Classroom Instruction with WebQuests: Connecting Literacy and Technology // Journal of Reading Education. – 2013. – № 2. – P. 31–38.
11. The Theory and Practice of Online Learning / ed. by Terry Anderson. – Edmonton, 2011. – 472 p.